

2026 General Assembly

5-7 May in Tulln, Austria

Forests in Austria

48 % area is forested

48 % Norway spruce, 4 % larch, 4% pine
11 % beech, 2 % oak,

Spruce: current

projected 2100

Annual growth: 29 Mm³, thereof 90% harvested

The forest-based industry in Austria

Universities

BOKU: materials, chemistry, construction

TU-Vienna: construction

TU-Graz: construction, paper

TU-Innsbruck: construction

Univ. of Applied Science

Secondary education

BOKU: AUSTRIA'S LEADING LIFE SCIENCES UNIVERSITY

FOUNDED: 1872

UNIVERSITY ORGANISATION: → RESEARCH, TEACHING

SCIENTISTS: → 2,166 (♀ 43.8%)

STUDENTS: → 10,042 (♀ 52.8%)

GRADUATES: → 1,396 (♀ 52.8%)

GENERAL STAFF: → 827 (♀ 58%)

Climate change, resource scarcity, biodiversity conservation, food security: The big questions of the future need answers. The field of science must address the problematic areas of politics, economics, management and NGOs today and find solutions which are understandable, relevant, and usable. BOKU is the only university in Austria which has devoted all its research and teaching to the Life Sciences.

6 BOKU COMPETENCE AREAS

ECOSYSTEM MANAGEMENT AND BIODIVERSITY

AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION AND FOOD

RENEWABLE RAW MATERIALS AND NEW TECHNOLOGIES

BIOTECHNOLOGY

LANDSCAPE, WATER, HABITAT AND INFRASTRUCTURE

RESOURCES AND SOCIAL DYNAMICS

COMET - Competence Centers for Excellent Technologies

The Austrian competence centre programme

Objectives

- Builds and strengthens key competences through excellent cooperative research.
- Pursues top-level international research and generates new ideas.
- Ensures continuous international benchmarking.
- Drives product, process, and service innovation for future markets.

Requirements

Consortium: At least one scientific partner and five company partners

Duration: 8 years (4+4)

Financing:

- 50% public funding
- Min. 5% by scientific partners
- Min. 40% by company partners
- Max. federal funding: 2 million Euro/year
- Max. federal funding: 1 million Euro/year

 Federal Ministry
Economy, Energy
and Tourism
Republic of Austria

 Federal Ministry
Innovation, Mobility
and Infrastructure
Republic of Austria

Partnership of the federal provinces OÖ and K with BOKU and JKU since 2001

CEO:
Boris Hultsch

Scientific director:
Wolfgang Gindl-Altmutter

Three research areas:

A1-Biorefinery processes and composite materials

A2-Wood Materials Technologies

A3-Smart Composites and Surfaces

Research area 2 - Wood Materials Technologies

Area manager:
Christian Hansmann

Evolution of the Centre

a) Personnel - Functions

b) Personnel - Gender

c) Personnel - Origin

PUBLICATIONS	VALUE 2025	ACCUMULATED SINCE 2001
Patents	3	75
Articles in refereed scientific journals	56	926
Articles in conference papers and book contributions	64	1.465
Scientific journals, newspaper articles, studies	109	899
Diploma, master and bachelor theses / finished	38	326
Dissertations ongoing Finished	33 20	119
Partner-Companies	> 100	

Main topics/methods

With a changed raw material supply to new, sustainable high-performance materials

Structural colour with nanocellulose

Superhydrophobicity by chemistry and texture

Ultra-strong wood

Integrated Fire Testing

- Small Scale Analytics
 - Chemical degradation pathways
 - STA / TG / DSC / STA-FTIR
- Screening Ignition Tests
 - Single Flame Test / UL-94
 - Smouldering / ignition rigs
- Bench Scale Fire Behaviour
 - Cone Calorimeter
 - Mini-SBI
 - Radiant Panel (Flooring)
- Long-Term Thermal Exposure
 - Heated storage container

Complete investigation chain from small to bench scale

Ongoing Research Projects

- Fundamental Fire Science
 - Auto-ignition of wood
 - Charcoal reactivity
 - Forest litter fire behaviour
- Engineered Wood Products
 - Adhesive thermal stability
 - Charring rate
- Flame Retardant Technologies
 - Novel FR systems
 - scCO₂ impregnation
- Applications:
 - Scientific studies
 - Material screening
 - Simulated EN 13501-1 classification
 - Development support for FR products

FR Birch

Reuse wooden building elements

phase #1
(2024)

phase #2
(2026)

Challenges and opportunities

- Changing raw material availability (species, quantity, predictability)
- Preservation vs. utilisation
- Carbon storage in forests vs storage in built wood
- Strategies for re-cycling and re-use
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Thank you!

Have a successful meeting in Tulln!